

A MOBILE UNDERSEA LABORATORY

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ABSTRACT

In order to allow scientists the opportunity to dive and spend extended periods of time on the seafloor, an undersea research laboratory, using a manned saturation habitat, has been developed by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA). The habitat will serve as a home and a laboratory for up to six scientists who will be able to live on the seafloor for periods from one week to a maximum of 30 days. This unique system design will enable scientists to perform long-term and continuous *in situ* research. Typical undersea experimental areas will include marine resources, seafloor ecology, pollution, diving physiology, aquanaut training and technology development.

Described will be the overall habitat system including a launch/recovery/ transport vehicle, habitat baseplate, life support buoy and the habitat itself. Also described will be the performance criteria, trade-off analyses, certification tests and operational scenarios associated with the various subsystems. Although the habitat is designed for depths to 120 feet of sea-water, trial operations in 50 feet of water are planned in 1987 off St. Croix, USVI. Because of the habitat's mobility, it is envisioned that the science program eventually will include the entire Caribbean region and involve up to 15 different countries.

1. INTRODUCTION

Marine researchers using SCUBA (Self Contained Underwater Breathing Apparatus) from the surface are restricted by the inherent limitation of traditional diving methods. These restrictions include limited bottom times because of decompression requirements and a limited amount of breathing gas. A manned saturation habitat, developed by NOAA, will allow scientists the opportunity to dive and spend extended periods of time on the seafloor in order to conduct *in situ* research.

There have been over 60 manned habitats in use over the past 20 years including AEGIR, TERTITE, HELGOLAND, and most recently HYDROLAB. In 12 years of operation off Florida, the Bahamas, and St. Croix, over 400 aquanauts have saturated for over 100,000 manhours in HYDROLAB, which was retired in July 1985. Habitat saturation diving

has become an important mode of support for marine research. The habitat described in this paper will be initially deployed as a replacement for HYDROLAB.

Conceptual design of the habitat system was initiated in 1980 by Southwest Research Institute under contract to the University of Southern California (USC) via a NOAA cooperative agreement. Major design requirements included: operation in water to 120 feet; living and laboratory accommodations for up to 6 aquanauts; capability to conduct missions of 7 to 30 days; and temperate water capability [1].

Primary engineering design of the habitat was conducted by Perry Oceanographic, Inc; the habitat was constructed, outfitted, and tested by VMW Industries/Mechidyne Systems Inc. under a USC contract from September 1984 to April 1986. Because of programmatic changes, a decision was made in late 1985 to relocate the habitat operational site from Catalina Island, CA, to St. Croix, USVI. Responsibility for future habitat operations was assigned in November 1985 to Fairleigh Dickinson University's (FDU) West Indies Laboratory via a grant from NOAA. With relocation to the Caribbean region, mobility became an important requirement since the habitat system would be relocated to different sites in response to science requirements [2]. In response to system mobility needs, a habitat baseplate and launch, recovery and transport vessel have been designed and constructed by Brown and Root Development, Inc. and Brown and Root Marine, Inc., respectively, under a FDU contract.

2. HABITAT SYSTEM DESCRIPTION

The habitat system consists of: a ballasted baseplate which holds the habitat to the ocean floor; a life support buoy (LSB) which provides water, air, and power; a launch, recovery and transport (LRT) vessel; and the habitat itself. The habitat, Figure 1, is basically a 9-foot-diameter, double-lock chamber capable of being moved to other research locations. It is designed to be operated independently of shore support, with life support functions supplied by the LSB. Other habitat system components will be described later.

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Figure 1. NOAA's Manned Saturation Habitat

Overall dimensions of the research habitat are 43 feet by 12 feet by 16.5 feet in height. The habitat shell is constructed from nominal 0.75 inch thick SA 516 grade 70 steel and incorporates numerous electrical and fluid penetrators. The habitat is divided into three compartments: a wet porch, entrance lock, and main lock. The 9' x 12' x 8' wet porch is an ambient pressure chamber which provides direct access to the sea through a large, rectangular hatch in the bottom. The wet porch, in addition to being used for diver suiting and filling air tanks, contains sorting trays and aquaria for scientists and various gas controls. The outer lock houses the sanitary facilities, environmental conditioning and control systems. The main chamber houses the sleeping area (6 fold-down bunks), laboratory equipment and counters, computers, environmental conditioning, and a galley including freezer, sink, and microwave. The living compartment also has two 24" diameter and five 10" diameter observation ports for monitoring marine experiments. Access between the compartments is facilitated by means of two large (24"W x 60"H) rectangular hatchways. Figure 2 depicts the internal arrangements.

3. FABRICATION AND TESTING

After the pressure hull was fabricated, it was internally hydrotested by the manufacturer at the factory. The tests were conducted in accordance with the American Society of Mechanical Engineering (ASME) Boiler and Pressure Code Section VIII and American Bureau of Shipping (ABS) Rules for Underwater Systems and Vehicles. The pressure levels were equivalent to 1.5 times (180 feet of seawater or 81 psi) the maximum operational depth of 120 fsw. Once these tests were completed, the pressure hull was shipped by flatbed truck from the fabrication contractor in Victoria, TX, to Carderock, MD, for external hydrotests.

The David Taylor Naval Ship Research and Development Center (DTNSRDC) facility was selected as the test location for numerous reasons. Costwise

and from a safety standpoint, it was advantageous to utilize a pressure tank test rather than an at-sea deployment. In addition, the DTNSRDC's 13-foot diameter pressure tank was one of the few tanks capable of holding the habitat hull. Again, the tests were conducted per the required ASME and ABS code specifications at an external pressure equivalent to 1.25 times the design depth or 68 psi. The 25-ton hull was carefully installed in a vertical attitude inside the pressure vessel and positioned on a three-point stand. The hull was completely filled with water and the volumetric discharge was monitored; the 1,900 ft³ habitat hull volume decreased approximately 0.75 ft³ at an external pressure of 68 psi.

After the hydrotesting was completed, the structure was sandblasted, painted, and outfitted with life support systems, scientific equipment and instrumentation, and household appliances (microwave oven, sinks, refrigerator, and a sanitary system). All components were hyperbarically tested at an equivalent pressure of 200 feet of seawater (fsw) to ensure proper operation after deployment on the seafloor environment. In addition, all pressure lines and gas panels were pressure tested at 1.5 times working pressure. The environmental control system was checked for compliance with the required temperature and humidity specifications. Carbon dioxide (CO₂) absorption tests were conducted in an emergency mode with only the CO₂ scrubbers operating and maintaining adequate levels of CO₂ per ABS requirements. All electrical functions and emergency power were verified. Functional tests were performed on all doors, hatches, gas and water lines, and electrical systems.

4. PRELIMINARY IN-WATER TESTING

Once the habitat had been completed, outfitted and in-plant tested, the habitat was loaded on a flatbed and trucked to Port Aransas, TX, for in-water testing. The purpose of these tests was: (a) to establish the proper trim and ballast conditions for the habitat in the free floating mode; (b) to test the function of the habitat hauldown system and baseplate latching mechanism for bottom installation; (c) to validate the wet porch integrity; and (d) to perform an inclining experiment for trim and stability handbook data.

When the habitat was floated, the hull was too buoyant and required negative buoyancy. With added lead ballast the total dry weight of the habitat was approximately 162,000 pounds. More in-water testing will be performed after the habitat has been modified for Caribbean operations.

5. DESIGN REQUIREMENTS FOR SYSTEM MOBILITY

Originally the habitat had been designed for long-term observations at a location near Catalina Island, California. Because of programmatic changes, a decision was made to transfer the habitat to the Caribbean region. With this relocation, mobility became a primary requirement since the habitat system would be moved periodically to Caribbean sites in response to science needs.

Figure 2. Port and Starboard Elevation Internal Views of the Habitat

Since system mobility was an important factor, a means for shipping and deploying the habitat was needed; also, a mobile baseplate for the habitat was required. It was therefore decided to develop a support vessel to transport the habitat and baseplate between sites. This support vessel, termed a launch recovery and transport (LRT) vessel, was designed to raise the habitat completely out of the water during transit. Also it would serve as a floating repair and maintenance facility for the habitat since there are virtually no cranes in the region capable of handling the 81-ton habitat. The LRT would also be a mobile support base (MSB) which would carry equipment such as deck decompression chamber, generators, air tanks, housing, and laboratory space required for saturated diving operations. This self-sufficiency would be required for habitat operations in remote Caribbean regions in order to provide utilities, support personnel, lodging, and emergency services.

In addition, a mobile baseplate design was required that would provide a secure and level foundation for the habitat on various seabeds at slopes up to 10 degrees. The baseplate would have to withstand extreme current and wave loading while maintaining the positively buoyant (45,000 pounds) habitat securely on bottom. The baseplate configuration will be designed so that heavy equipment such as cranes, pile drivers or barges would not be required during deployment.

6. TRADE-OFF ANALYSIS AND CONCEPTUAL DESIGN

In response to the requirements for system mobility and self-sufficiency, a trade-off analysis was conducted on three proposed designs for habitat launch, recovery and transport (LRT) platforms and habitat baseplates. This study was conducted to assist in the selection of optimum design combinations. A total of 11 parameters, including costs, safety, operating complexity, mobility, and mission performance aspects were selected and weighted. A scoring criteria listing for each parameter also was developed. Engineering tasks beyond the usual conceptual design studies were conducted to reduce or eliminate major technical and economic risks and to achieve an adequate engineering description of the LRT vessel and habitat baseplate so that the basic system design would not significantly change during the subsequent detailed design [3].

7. LAUNCH, RECOVERY AND TRANSPORT (LRT) VESSEL DESCRIPTION

A trade-off analysis determined that a twin hull catamaran was the optimum design vessel for habitat support operations. The habitat will be deployed through a 48-foot by 28-foot moon pool between the catamaran hulls. After considering the required lift and carrying capacity, the vessel weight, aspects of impact stability, minimum draft requirements and future growth capability, the catamaran hull dimensions were established: depth-12 feet; beam-11 feet; length between perpendiculars-84 feet. The catamaran vessel has a 50-foot beam and is 100 feet long.

LENGTH OVERALL	99'6"
MOLDED DEPTH	12'0"
MOLDED BREADTH	50'0"
DRAFT, FULL LOAD	8'6"
DRAFT, LIGHT SHIP	5'1"
DISPLACEMENT, FULL LOAD	448.6 t
DISPLACEMENT, LIGHT SHIP	255.6 t

Figure 3. Launch, Recovery and Transport (LRT) Vessel with Habitat

The selected dimensions and layout will permit simple and safe operations, i.e., deployment and retrieval of the habitat and its baseplate, through the LRT moon pool using four davits and winches. This design allows the LRT to function as a conventional surface vessel requiring no submergence which results in reasonably sized scantlings. Another feature is that ample space and volume are available on the LRT for future growth. The LRT can be outfitted to serve as a mobile support base and can be further modified to provide self-propulsion and position-keeping capabilities.

Four fixed davits are positioned at the moon pool to allow handling of the 81-ton habitat and 118-ton baseplate. The hook height of the davits allows the habitat to be raised, stored and the baseplate to be separately raised within the moon pool. Figure 3 depicts the habitat being transported by the LRT.

The LRT will comply with all applicable requirements of the American Bureau of Shipping (ABS). It will be classed as a Maltese Cross A1 Barge as an unmanned and non-propelled platform. The LRT

design also is in compliance with United States Coast Guard (USCG) requirements.

8. HABITAT BASEPLATE

The habitat requires a baseplate to provide an anchoring/latching surface for habitat placement on the seafloor. The baseplate was designed for: maximum wave heights of 20 feet; with wave periods up to 15 seconds and 3-knot currents. A detailed hydrodynamic model of both the habitat and baseplate was used to evaluate the hydrodynamic loads on the structures. A shallow water, three-dimensional, potential theory model, assuming a water depth of 60 feet was used to quantify the vertical and horizontal forces and the overturning moments.

The 21-foot by 40-foot, 118 ton, baseplate consists of a tubular framework of 30-inch diameter steel pipes. Four leveling legs allow deployment on ocean floor slopes of ± 10 degrees. The leveling assembly consists of four hydraulic impact wrench operated screwjacks. Each leveling leg has a large (8 foot square) U-joint affixed pad which allows self-alignment to the local seafloor contour. In order to provide on-bottom

Figure 4. Deployment of Habitat using the Launch, Recovery and Transport (LRT) Vessel

stability during severe environmental conditions and to counter the habitat's 45,000 pound positive buoyancy, the baseplate on-bottom weight had to be maximized. Lead was selected as the ballast material; because of its high density, the out-of-water weight of the baseplate was minimized. Also, since the lead was positioned in the baseplate legs the overturning moment resistance was maximized and the overall hydrodynamic profile lessened during deployment and operations.

9. HABITAT LIFE SUPPORT BUOY

Since the habitat is not designed for autonomous operations, a surface platform, termed a life support buoy (LSB), provides power, air and potable water to the habitat via a 125-foot umbilical. During emergency conditions the habitat has on-board life support for 6 people for 72 hours and for a complete decompression from maximum depth.

The LSB, designed and outfitted by NURP/FDU personnel, is basically a reinforced 43-foot enclosed boat hull which has been configured for unattended operations. It houses the habitat's environmental control unit (ECU), a 100 KW diesel generator, a 7 KW standby generator, electric and diesel high-pressure and low-pressure air compressors, a reverse osmosis desalination system

with a 225 gallon water tank, and two 625 gallon diesel tanks. An 8-inch diameter umbilical, 125 feet long, provides air, power, water and communications to the habitat. The LSB, habitat and a shore-based support station are linked with hard wire communications.

10. HABITAT DEPLOYMENT PROCEDURE

The first step in the launch scenario is to tow the LRT with the habitat and baseplate secured on board, to the deployment site. Next, the LRT is anchored and the baseplate lowered slowly to the bottom using the four davits. After the baseplate is on the bottom, divers check for levelness; divers use hydraulic impact wrenches to adjust the screwjacks on the four corners of the baseplate so that it is leveled within ± 0.5 degrees.

Next the habitat is prepared for descent with all systems having been tested and proven operational. The habitat is slowly lowered into the water with the four davits. Once the habitat is submerged under the LRT, habitat ballast tanks are dewatered, and the davit cables are unhooked by divers and the positively buoyant habitat (Figure 4) is winched to the bottom with three hydraulic winches located on the baseplate. After the habitat rests on the baseplate, it is securely attached with

latching levers. Finally, the flooded wet porch is blown down (dewatered) using air pressure and the habitat is ready for operation after umbilical hookup with the life support buoy (LSB).

11. OPERATIONAL SCENARIO

Training and qualification of the habitat scientific team are conducted prior to the start of each mission. Both in-water and classroom training sessions are held to familiarize the aquanauts with the operation of the habitat, modified diving equipment and safety procedures. Upon completion of required pre-dive checklists, the aquanauts SCUBA to the habitat. An onboard technician will conduct the daily habitat checks, replenish carbon dioxide absorbent and perform any required maintenance. Life support parameters are monitored at the shore operations base with a data link and packet radio from the habitat and LSB.

The aquanauts routinely spend up to 9 hours a day working on their experiments on the seafloor. A video system allows monitoring of experiments and surface conditions. An on-board computer and data link are used to gather experimental data. After undersea experiments have been completed, decompression of the aquanauts must be conducted and is accomplished by slowly reducing the pressure inside the habitat to surface atmospheric pressure. When the aquanauts reach surface pressure, after approximately 20 hours of decompression, they exit the habitat and swim to the surface. The staff physician examines the aquanauts for signs of decompression sickness or other medical problems.

To enhance undersea research capabilities, a comprehensive environmental monitoring system will be developed. This instrumentation suite will include a data acquisition system, recorder, a two-axis solid state ocean current meter, conductivity-temperature-pressure (CTP) and dissolved oxygen (DO) sensors, transmissometer and wave height measurement capability. An acoustic tracking system able to monitor multiple diver locations and depths on a continuous basis will be developed.

12. NURP-FDU CARIBBEAN SCIENCE PROGRAM

The new mobile habitat system will be the primary platform used to support a science program that is Caribbean-wide in scope. NOAA's National Undersea Research Program (NURP) will support research projects that address areas of particular importance for the Caribbean and which meet NOAA's undersea mission objectives. Examples of such research areas are:

Biological Productivity and Living Resources - larval recruitment processes and reproductive biology of reef fishes and invertebrates; evaluation of new fisheries species/stocks; primary and secondary production processes; food web studies; benthic/pelagic coupling.

Coastal, Oceanic, and Estuarine Processes - production and transport of carbonate sands; benthic nutrient regeneration and

its contribution to primary productivity; history of sea level changes and sea surface temperatures; role of groundwater and terrestrial run-off in tropical coastal environments.

Pathways and Fate of Materials in the Ocean - effects of pollutants, sediment loading, hurricanes, dredging, blasting, and eutrophication on coral reef ecosystems; processes of recovery.

Ocean Services - oxygen toxicity effects; biofouling and corrosion; assessment of biomedicinals in Caribbean biota; physiological and psychological effects of hyperbaric conditions.

For 1988, the areas of research concentration at NURP-FDU are: recruitment processes in marine organisms, and nutrient cycling and the control of primary productivity in reef ecosystems. Investigators are encouraged to submit proposals that outline an integrated, multi-disciplinary approach to problems within the above areas of research concentration and require use of this undersea laboratory. It is anticipated that the mobility of the new habitat system will facilitate undersea research in the region by allowing parallel investigations over a large geographic area, as well as supporting study of problems unique to particular Caribbean locations.

Additional information about proposed habitat operations, relevant research topics, and submission of science proposals may be obtained directly from the Science Director, NOAA's National Undersea Research Program at Fairleigh Dickinson University, West Indies Laboratory, Teague Bay, Christiansted, St. Croix, U.S. Virgin Islands, or from the Program Scientist, NOAA's Office of Undersea Research, Rockville, MD.

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